

POWER QUALITY IMPROVEMENT FOR NON LINEAR LOAD USING SIX PULSE CONVERTER WITH PASSIVE SHUNT FILTER

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the waveform distortion and harmonics reduction of distribution transformer with the help of passive shunt filter. This study examines the effect of harmonic distortion on power transformers when supplying non-sinusoidal load currents. A synchronized 6-Pulse generator is used to fire the six thyristors of a six-pulse converter. The output of the converter is a vector of six pulses individually synchronized on the six thyristor voltages. The pulses are generated alpha degrees after the increasing zero crossings of the thyristor commutation voltages. The line current harmonics cause increase in losses, instability, and also voltage distortion. Shunt filters still dominate the harmonic compensation at medium/high voltage level, whereas active filters have been proclaimed for low/medium voltage ratings. Passive filtering has been preferred for harmonic compensation in distribution systems due to low cost simplicity, reliability, and control less operation. In modern electrical distribution systems there has been a sudden increase of harmonics because of single phase and three-phase non-linear loads. These non-linear loads are cause of harmonics. Passive shunt filter have been used traditionally for mitigating the distortion due to harmonic current in industrial power systems. Simulink model is design through MATLAB Software.

Keywords: Power quality, harmonics, passive filter, transformer, non-linear load.

1. INTRODUCTION

Power quality is a serious concern in electric power system, different type's disturbances like voltage sag, voltage swell, fluctuation, noise, flickers, waveform distortion and harmonics take place. The intensive use of power converters and non-linear loads has contributed for the deterioration of the power quality and this factor affects critical processes, resulting in substantial economic losses [1], [5]. The devices based on power electronics directed to improve power quality are denominated as "Custom-Power" [2]. One Custom-Power device can be obtained from the collective operation of an active filter with a passive filter, which results in a hybrid filter. The hybrid filter used in this work consists of shunt passive filters operating with a series active filter [1] [3]. Nonlinear loads such as saturated coils and transformers are the main cause of producing harmonics in power system. Most of the pollution issues are created due to the nonlinear characteristics [4] and fast switching of Power electronics. Classically, shunt passive filters, mainly consist of tuned LC filters and or high passive filters are used to reduce the harmonics [5] and power capacitors are used to improve the power factor [6]. But they have the limitations of fixed compensation, large size and can also exile resonance conditions [7]. Transformers, motors, cables, interrupters and capacitors are the some equipment which is affected by harmonics converters mainly

produces notches and they basically affect the electronic control devices [8]. There are two routes to the reduction of power quality problems. The first way is known as load conditioning, which assures that the equipment is made less sensitive and effective to power disturbances [9]. The second technique is, to install line-conditioning systems that counteract or suppress the power system disturbances. In distribution systems passive filters have been used to limit of harmonic currents [10].

2. PASSIVE FILTERS

Passive filters were preferred in the earlier time for harmonic reimbursement because they are simple in structure and easy to install different topologies of passive filters. They are mostly categorized into series and shunt passive filters [11]. Series passive filters use high series impedance to block harmonics, and shunt filters divert harmonics by means of a low impedance shunt path. The series filters must be designed to carry full load current [9], [12], whereas shunt filters carry only a fraction of the current that a series filter carries. Also shunt filters, if properly designed, supply reactive power to the load at the fundamental frequency [13]. The shunt passive filter is assembled with passive elements resistance, inductance and capacitance. When the inductive and capacitive reactance of the passive filter become equal at a particular harmonic frequency, shunt passive filter acts as low impedance path for that harmonic component [14].

The selection of these element ratings depends on [14-17]

- Reactive power to be inserted
- Harmonics to be diminished
- Quality factor of the tuned filter circuit
- Tolerance in supply-frequency endorsed
- Tolerance in filter capacitance and inductance value due to ageing and temperature changes.

Shunt passive filters are once more classified as single tuned, double tuned, high pass damped filters [15]. A single tuned filter is a series RLC circuit tuned for particular harmonic frequency, whereas double tuned filter is tuned for two harmonic frequencies [16]. The double-tuned filter is preferred mainly in high-voltage applications, because of the reduction in the number of inductors to be subjected to full line voltages [17]. Triple- and quadruple-tuned filters are rarely used because of the difficulty of adjustment of filter components. Automatically tuned filters use a control system [18], which measures the fundamental frequency reactive power to be compensated by the filter and uses the information to automatically switch the capacitance or to vary the inductance [19]. In order to understand the effectiveness of shunt passive filter in compensating reactive power and harmonics of typical nonlinear load, phase controller for varying power consumed by a series R-L element, is considered [20].

3. DIFFERENT TYPES OF PASSIVE FILTERS

The classification of Passive filter is done on the type of harmonic generation component source present in the system & passive component sys resistor, inductor & capacitor connected in the system & are given as

- Passive Series Filter
- Passive Shunt Filter
- passive Hybrid Filter

A very classical type of passive filter is shown in the figure where filter is connected in the parallel with distribution system through power common coupling point having nonlinear load characteristics.

3.1. Passive Series Filter- The system which come with the voltage source type harmonic which are the product of diode rectifier with R-L connected load it is prefer to use the series type passive filter as considered as potential remedy of harmonic mitigation [21].

Figure 1 Basic structure of Passive Series Filter

Passive type series filter has property of purely inductive type or LC tuned characteristics. The main component of passive series filter is AC line reactor & DC link filter [2], [19]. Series passive filter is given by these two components connected in series that AC line reactor improves system magnitude of inductance in system that alters the path of current drawn in the rectifier circuit [18].

3.2. Passive Shunt Filter- It is the most common method for the cancellation of harmonic current in the distribution system. Passive harmonic filter are basically designed on principle of either single tuned or band pass filter technology. As the name suggests shunt type filter are connected in system parallel with load [1-6].

Figure 2 Basic structure of Passive Shunt Filter

Passive filter offer a very low impedance in the network at the tuned frequency to divert all the related current & at given tuned frequency [1]. Because of passive filter always have tendency of offering some reactive power in the circuit so the design of passive shunt filter take place for the two purpose. One is the filtering purpose & another one is to provide reactive compensation purpose of correcting power factor in the circuit at desired level [3-6]. The advantage with the passive shunt type filter is that it only carry fraction of current so the whole system AC power losses are reduced compare to series type filter [13]. The given figure shows the schematic diagram of 6 pulse converter system connected with shunt passive type filter which are simply employed ever connection in distribution system have R-L load in system [7], [11].

3.3. Passive Hybrid Filter- Hybrid filters combine a number of passive and/or active filters and their structure may be of series or parallel topology or a combination of the two [16]. They can be installed in single-phase, three-phase three-wire, and three-phase four-wire distorted systems [21]. The passive circuit performs basic filtering action at the dominant harmonic frequencies (e.g., 5th or 7th) whereas the active elements, through precise control, mitigate higher harmonics [1-3]. This will effectively reduce the overall size and cost of active filtering. The use of passive shunt filter creates the problem of voltage regulation at light loads. It also increases the dc voltage ripple and ac peak current of the rectifier [13], [19]. On the other hand, passive series filter suffers from lagging power factor operation as well as the voltage drop across the filter components both at fundamental frequency as well as harmonic frequencies [21].

Figure 3 Basic structure of Passive Hybrid Filter

To overcome these drawbacks, a combination of both these configurations is presented as passive hybrid filter [10]. This configuration is able to supplement the shortfalls of both these passive filters and simultaneously it results in improvement in harmonic compensation characteristics for varying load condition even under stiff and distorted ac mains voltage [12], [14].

4. SIMULINK MODEL AND RESULT PERFORMANCE FOR PASSIVE SHUNT FILTER BASED CONVERTER WITH RL LOAD

To demonstrate the performance of these passive filters feeding a three-phase converter with R-L load, these passive filters are modeled in MATLAB environment along with simulink and power system block set toolboxes. Different components of these converters such as low pass filter with R- L load are simulated. Distribution transformer primary winding is connected with source and secondary is connected with the load. The secondary winding of distribution transformer is load connected winding or load side winding.

Figure 4 Simulink model for RL load without six-pulse converter and passive shunt filter

5. RESULT AND PERFORMANCE OF SIMULINK MODEL FOR PASSIVE SHUNT FILTER BASED SIX PULSE CONVERTER WITH RL LOAD

Figure 5 Three Phase voltage source

Figure 6 Three Phase current source

Figure 7 Three phase transformer- primary winding side Phase A, B and C voltage (a), (b), (c) respectively without passive shunt filter

Figure 8 Three phase transformer-secondary winding side Phase A, B and C voltage (a), (b) and (c) respectively without passive shunt filter

6. RESULT AND PERFORMANCE OF SIMULINK MODEL FOR RL LOAD- SIX PULSE CONVERTER WITH PASSIVE SHUNT FILTER

Figure 9 Simulink model for RL connected load with six pulse converter and passive shunt filter

The Simulink model block implements a three-phase zero-impedance voltage source. The common node (neutral) of the three sources is accessible through input N of the block. Time variation for the amplitude, phase and frequency of the fundamental can be pre-programmed. In addition, two harmonics can be superimposed on the fundamental. MATLAB model of a passive series filter based six pulse ac- dc converters with R-L load. Depending on the harmonic spectrum of the supply current, the passive filters designed are low pass filter tuned for 5th order harmonic frequency. The subsystem named shunt filter consists of 5th harmonic frequency. Based on the design carried out the filter component values are $L=15e-3$, $C=25e-6$, $R=0.80$.

Figure 10 Three phase voltage source

Figure 11 Three phase current source

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 12 Three phase transformer- primary winding side Phase A,B and C voltage (a), (b), (c) respectively with passive shunt filter

Figure 13 Three phase transformer-secondary winding side Phase A voltage with passive shunt filter

Figure 14 Three phase transformer-secondary winding side Phase B voltage with passive shunt filter

Figure 15 Three phase transformer-secondary winding side Phase C Voltage with passive shunt filter

7. CONCLUSION

The presented single-phase shunt active power filter has demonstrated to be able to improve distorted waveform and compensate the harmonic currents and the power factor produced by loads, making the current at the source side to become almost sinusoidal and in

phase with the system voltage. This current compensation can also prevent voltage harmonics and improvement of waveform distortion for transformer. Simulink model using MATLAB Simulink is proven to be very useful for studying the detailed behavior of the system for harmonic and unbalance compensation, under steady state and transients. The total harmonic distortion of source current is reduced when shunt active power filter is connected to the power system at the point of common coupling. The effect of multiple harmonic sources can be investigated by applying the superposition principle.

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APPENDIX

These constraints are used to design Simulink model:

Components	Specification
AC Source	$V_s=400\text{v}$, $f=50\text{ Hz}$
Non-linear Load	Universal bridge $R=40, (\Omega)$ $L=50\text{e-}3\text{ (H)}$
Passive Filter	$R=0.80$ $L=16\text{e-}3$, $C=25\text{e-}6$